

Why small states offer answers to important questions in international relations: Rethinking power and agency

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Abstract: This essay illustrates the importance of small state studies for answering important questions in international relations, such as ‘what is power?’ and ‘what is agency?’. Understanding small state agency as graded and contingent, it argues that a relational perspective on power and agency grounded in the study of small states is key for creating a more pluralist and nuanced understanding of both the challenges and opportunities of individual states and the fabric of international relations. A relational perspective allows us to analyse concrete challenges and opportunities for small states navigating asymmetrical relationships with stronger actors inside and outside international institutions, and to explore the nature, dynamics, and impact of relations in international relations more generally.

Keywords: agency, international relations, power, relationalism, small states

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Introduction

The history of international relations is typically told in terms of war and peace between great powers. Nodal points in international and diplomatic history, such as the Peace of Westphalia, the Congress of Vienna, and the end of the Cold War, are interpreted through the eyes of the most consequential actors and the implications of their victories, defeats, and visions for international order. Similarly, most theoretical contributions to the study of international relations extrapolate the behaviour of one or more great powers into supposedly general theorising on ‘states’ in international relations. As (in)famously summed up by Kenneth Waltz in his aptly titled *Theory of International Politics*, “[a] general theory of international politics is necessarily based on the great powers” (Waltz, 1979, p. 73). Consequently, small states have typically been viewed as “marginal actors in the arena of international politics” (Willis, 2021, p. 26), or – to the extent they are awarded agency – as victims, free-riders, and disruptors of international order (Cooley and Nexon, 2020).

This perspective creates some unfortunate blind spots concerning the behaviours, policies, challenges and opportunities of small states, and even more importantly, concerning fundamental concepts and challenges in international relations. Consequently, and inspired by Veenendaal & Corbett (2015), studying small states offers important answers to several essential questions in international relations, including: What is power? What is agency?

Power

Fundamentally, the study of small states challenges conventional understandings of power in international relations. Most often, these understandings take their point of departure from a structuralist realist understanding of relative power, focusing mainly (but not necessarily exclusively) on material capabilities. To be sure, the (lack or scarcity of) material capabilities and assets are important for the ecologies of risk and generalised cost structures faced by small states in an anarchic international system as these tend to vary with polarity (Pedi and Wivel,

2022). But the concrete challenges and opportunities of small states typically depend on the small states' ability to navigate asymmetrical relationships with stronger actors inside and outside international institutions (Baldacchino and Wivel, 2020). This relational understanding of power in international relations allows us to explore and explain variations in challenges, opportunities, and policy options across different regions and policy areas (Long, 2022), and why and how some relationships are regarded as "special" by one or more participants (Haugevik, 2018). Such questions are important – not only to small states, but to states in general.

Even more importantly, this relational understanding points to an understudied and often overlooked – but hugely important – part of the fabric of international relations: relationships. Understanding the characteristics and implications of relational power is likely to become even more important as the world is becoming more multi-order (Flockhart, 2016), or multiplex (Acharya, 2017), and regional orders are increasingly characterised by a combination of conflictual and cooperative relationships. Understanding the dynamics of these relationships is significant to the challenges and opportunities faced by all types of states, regardless of size (Paul and Kornprobst, 2025). The war in Ukraine is illustrative of this increasing role: the chance of victory for either Ukraine or Russia is heavily contingent upon their relationships with important international actors, such as the United States, China, North Korea, Iran and the EU, whilst the willingness and ability of these actors to help is conditioned by their relationship with each other, as well as with other states, e.g., in the Global South.

Agency

A focus on small states also holds important clues to understanding agency in international relations. Much international relations research begins from a highly stylised understanding of the agency of great powers: they are understood as self-contained actors with the ability to make independent decisions and the capacity to implement those decisions in world politics. According to this understanding, variations in decision-making and implementation may be caused or constituted by such factors as military heft, economic costs and benefits, the personalities or perceptions of political leaders, or socially constituted norms and practices, depending on the ontological and epistemological starting points of the analysis. However, no matter the starting point, agency is viewed as an either/or question: either you are an international actor (typically a state) with foreign policy agency, or you are not.

A focus on small states allows us to problematise and qualify this understanding. As argued by Iver B. Neumann, we may usefully understand the agency of small states as graded and contingent upon "how collective, systems-level knowledge about what a small state is interacts with small-state agency itself to yield a specific kind of agency for each and every small state within a system" (Neumann, 2023, p. 59). In this understanding, small state agency is constituted in the meeting between national and collective role constructions. This is not to say that material conditions do not matter, as they may still influence the competence and performance of small states and how they are viewed by themselves as well as others (although, in practice, this may be difficult to tell apart from more ideational factors).

While there are many examples of graded agency in the small state literature – mostly showing how small states "punch above their weight", i.e. perform more agency than we would expect from their relative power – this argument is also relevant to great powers and middle powers. As illustrated by, e.g., the war in Ukraine, the repertoire of agency available to a great power is dependent not only on the great power's own role conception but on the role conceptions of a variety of other states and non-state actors, such as military alliances, the international press, and the United Nations. At large, the theory and the practice of small states

in international relations remind us that graded agency in international relations, like agency in general, is, at the same time, material, social, and judicial. This calls for a multidimensional understanding of agency, not only for small states, but for international actors more broadly.

Conclusion

Students of great power politics tend to exaggerate the generalisability of their findings for international relations. This is damaging to a full and nuanced understanding of international relations. However, the tendency of students of small state politics to understate the generalisability of their findings and emphasise the uniqueness of each small state may be just as bad. Mainstreaming the study of small states in international relations and avoiding “exceptionalism and exoticism” in the depiction of small states hold important promise, not only for advancing the study of small states proper (Baldacchino, 2018, p. 11), but also for informing the study of international relations in general. Thus, studying small states offers important answers to important questions in international relations, such as what is power and what is agency. This essay has argued the value of answering these questions from a relational point of departure. We may build on this approach to engage with recent advances in so-called deep relationalism to think critically about international relations, as well as the hierarchies and asymmetries of knowledge production (Klasche and Poopuu, 2023). From this point of departure, we may ask: Who speaks about power and agency in the study of international relations, how do they speak about these issues, and why do they conclude and generalise as they do? This line of inquiry would allow for a more pluralistic and nuanced understanding of international relations, as well as a more diverse study of small state politics.

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